

Conversion of solar energy to chemical energy

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Abstract : The rate of evolution of hydrogen from water by photochemical process using solar energy has been investigated employing fourteen metal complexes as catalysts, ten electron relays, three electron donors and two co-catalysts in different permutation and combinations. The effect of varying reaction conditions like temperature, concentration and pH have also been investigated for the optimum production of hydrogen by the photochemical cleavage of water molecules.

Keywords : Solar energy, chemical energy, photosensitizer.

Introduction

The increasing demand for fossil fuels has led scientists to develop alternate sources of energy. Sooner or later these fossil fuels will be completely depleted and in this context solar energy appears to be very promising. The most ideal situation for trapping the solar energy involves a chemical reaction of water in the presence of suitable catalyst. Photoproduct with increased free energy is formed by the absorption of sunlight in this process and the photoproduct reconverts itself into the starting material with liberation of energy. Photochemical cleavage of water molecules have been widely studied for energy storage¹, since the starting material water is abundant, inexpensive and safe to operate. As water can not

directly absorb sunlight, some means of sensitization is required. Excited state redox potentials of some metal complexes are utilized in effecting the oxidation to produce oxygen and hydrogen respectively. The reduction potential for half-cell reactions for eqs. (1) and (2) are -0.4 and + 0.82 respectively at pH 7 and 760 torr.

Tris(2,2'-bipyridine)Ru^{II} dication satisfies many of the requirements^{2,3} to act as a catalyst for photochemical cleavage of water molecule to hydrogen and oxygen. The basic reaction cycles for hydrogen and oxygen evolution are given in the Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Although lot of work has been done using ruthenium complexes as photosensitizers⁴, a systematic study has not been reported till now on the effect of the different substituents on the photosensitizing effect of tris(2,2'-bipyridine)Ru^{II} dication. It is also of interest to study the effect of newer electron relays, co-catalysts and electron donors. In the cleavage of water molecules, the key step in the photochemical reaction involves an electron transfer from Ru^{II} cation to a suitable electron acceptor. During this process Ru^{II} converts to Ru^{III}. In this regard it would be interesting to study the effect of electron withdrawing and electron donating groups in the complex on the overall production of hydrogen. To study the effect of temperature, concentration and pH on the rate of evolution of hydrogen will also be interesting. Hence, we propose systematic investigations of the following aspects regarding the photo evolution of hydrogen.

(i) Study of H₂ evolution in terms of rate and yield using different combinations of metal complexes, electron relays, co-catalysts and electron donors.

(ii) Study of H₂ evolution under varying reaction conditions like temperature, concentration and pH etc.

Results and discussion

The summary of results on the rate of evolution of hydrogen is reported in Tables 1–4. The Table 1 gives the data of hydrogen production for a set of experiments in which only the electron relay is changed. In each experiment and all other components viz. photosensitizer, electron donor and the co-catalyst are kept unchanged. The results in the Table 2 show the amount of hydrogen produced by changing the photosensitizer in each experiment while other components remain same. Table 3 shows production of hydrogen with varying sacrificial electron donor and Table 4 gives results obtained by varying the co-catalyst. The results obtained in our study reveal the fact that the electron donating groups (viz. methyl) at 4,4'-positions of the ligand 2,2'-bipyridine [complex 16] enhances the rate of hydrogen evolution and the yield on exposure to sunlight. On the other hand the presence of electron withdrawing groups in the complexes 17 and 18 reduce the rate and yields of hydrogen production on exposure to sunlight.

Table 1. Hydrogen generation by the photochemical cleavage of water molecules using various electron relays

Photosensitizer : Tris(2,2'-bipyridine)Ru^{II} dication (15).
co-catalyst : Pt/PVA, sacrificial electron donor : ethylenediaminetetraacetate, Temp. 30 °C, pH = 5

Sl. no.	Electron relay	Amount of H ₂ produced (mL/h)
1.	(29)	2.4
2.	(30)	1.3
3.	(31)	2.8
4.	(32)	2.0
5.	(33)	1.0
6.	(34)	1.8
7.	(35)	2.0
8.	(36)	2.6
9.	(22)	0.8
10.	(23)	1.0

Table 2. Sensitizing effects of metal complexes on hydrogen evolution by the photochemical cleavage of water molecules

Electron relay : *N,N'*-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridinium dichloride (29).
co-catalyst : Pt/PVA, sacrificial electron donor : ethylenediaminetetraacetate, Temp. 30 °C, pH = 5

Sl. no.	Photosensitizer	Amount of H ₂ produced (mL/h)
1.	[Ru(2,2'-bipy) ₃]I ₂ (15)	2.4
2.	[Ru(4,4'-dime-2,2'-bipy) ₃]I ₂ (16)	3.0
3.	[Ru(4,4'-dichloro-2,2'-bipy) ₃]I ₂ (17)	2.0
4.	[Ru(4,4'-dicarboxy-2,2'-bipy) ₃]I ₂ (18)	1.0
5.	[Ru(NH ₃) ₄ (py) ₂]I ₂ (19)	Nil
6.	[Ru(NH ₃) ₄ (4-Me-py) ₂]I ₂ (20)	Nil
7.	[Ru(NH ₃) ₄ (3-Me-py) ₂]I ₂ (21)	Nil
8.	[Rh(2,2'-bipy) ₃]Cl ₃ (22)	Nil
9.	[Rh(4,4'-dime-2,2'-bipy) ₃]Cl ₃ (23)	Nil
10.	[Rh(en) ₃]Cl ₃ (24)	Nil
11.	[Rh(py) ₄ (Cl ₂)]Cl (25)	Nil
12.	[Ru(<i>N,N'</i> -dioxide of 2,2'-bipy) ₃]Cl ₂ (26)	Nil
13.	[Ru(MHBQ) ₂] (27)	Nil
14.	[Ru(PHBQ) ₂] (28)	Nil

(1) py = pyridine, (2) 4,4'-dime-2,2'-bipy = 4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-bipyridine, (3) 4,4'-dichloro-2,2'-bipy = 4,4'-dichloro-2,2'-bipyridine, (4) MHBQ = 2-methyl-3-(2-hydroxybenzylamino)quinazolin-(3*H*)-4-one, (5) PHBQ = 2-phenyl-3-(2-hydroxybenzylamino)quinazolin-(3*H*)-4-one.

Table 3. Comparison of the activities of sacrificial electron donors in the photochemical production of hydrogen by the cleavage of water molecules

Photosensitizer : Tris(2,2'-bipyridine)Ru^{II} dication (15), co-catalyst : Pt/PVA, electron relay : *N,N'*-diallyl-2,2'-bipyridinium dibromide (31), Temp. 30 °C and pH = 5

Sl. no.	Sacrificial electron donor	Amount of H ₂ produced (mL/h)
1.	Ethylenediaminetetraacetate	2.8
2.	Triethanolamine	2.0
3.	<i>N</i> -Ethylmorpholine	2.3

Table 4. Comparison of the activities of co-catalysts in the photochemical production of hydrogen from water molecules

Photosensitizer : Tris(2,2'-bipyridine)Ru^{II} dication (15), electron relay : *N,N'*-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridinium dichloride (29), Temp. 30 °C and pH=5

Sl. no.	Co-catalyst	Amount of H ₂ produced (mL/h)
1.	Pt/PVA	2.4
2.	Ru/PVA	1.0

The order of rate and amount of hydrogen production is as follows :

This difference can be attributed to electron donating and electron withdrawing effects of the substituents present in the ligands of the complex. This supports our view on the mechanism of cleavage of water molecules where elec-

tron transfer process is involved from the complex to the electron relay. An electron donating group therefore facilitates this step with increased rate of hydrogen evolution. Of the fourteen complexes studied, only four of them i.e. 15-18 are found to be active catalysts for production of hydrogen. The remaining ten complexes 19-28 are found to be inactive. This can be attributed to unfavourable redox potentials of the Ru²⁺/Ru³⁺ couple, which reflects on the ability of electron transfer of the excited complex molecule. Change in the ligand structure in the complex may lead to an unfavourable condition where inter conversion of Ru²⁺ and Ru³⁺ is prevented to a large extent. In other words, the reaction becomes almost irreversible and no hydrogen evolution takes place. Similar reasons could be attributed for the inability of rhodium complexes to act as photosensitizers. Of the ten electron relays we have studied, the *N,N'*-diallyl-2,2'-bipyridinium dibromide (31) is found to be the most efficient in the photochemical production of hydrogen from water, while *N,N'*-dibenzyl-2,2'-bipyridinium dibromide (33) is the least efficient. The remaining eight other elec-

tron relays viz. 22, 23, 29, 30, 32, 34, 35 and 36 showed moderate to lower efficiencies. The function of electron relay is to accept an electron from Ru²⁺ to become a radical cation as shown below.

L = 2,2'-bipyridine

Here, it may be mentioned that the relative ease of acceptance of an electron from the complex by the electron relay to give the radical cation is a function of redox potentials of the structures A and B.

It is known, that those systems which fall in the range of -0.4 to -0.6 V redox potentials will be active for hydrogen production. Of the three electron donors studied, ethylenediaminetetraacetate (EDTA) was found to be highly satisfactory at pH 5 for the rate of production of hydrogen. The other two donors i.e. triethanolamine and *N*-ethylmorpholine are less efficient. Colloidal platinum on poly(vinylalcohol) was found to be more active than colloidal ruthenium on poly(vinylalcohol). Similar observations were made by Grätzel *et al.* using only one electron relay and one photosensitizer. We have confirmed this observation using five electron relays and two photosensitizers. We have investigated the effect of varying the pH and temperature of the system. It was found that the ideal conditions for photochemical production of hydrogen are pH 5 and 30 °C. Addition of inorganic salts was found to be detrimental to the rate of production of hydrogen. The results obtained in this study can be summarized as follows :

(i) Electron donating groups at 4,4'-position of the ligand 2,2'-bipyridine enhance the rate and yield of hydrogen production while the electron withdrawing groups in the same positions show a reverse effect.

(ii) The optimum temperature and pH for the reaction are 30 °C and pH 5 respectively.

(iii) Colloidal Pt/PVA is more effective than colloidal Ru/PVA.

(iv) Efficient electron transfer process and long term stability of the photosensitizer in the photochemical process seem to be the key factors in the hydrogen production.

Experimental

Preparation of ligands :

Ligands used in the preparation of complexes 15, 19-22, 24 and 25 are commercially available. Other ligands are prepared either according to the standard literature procedures or with slight experimental modifications. 4,4'-Dichloro-2,2'-bipyridine (1) was prepared according to the method of Case *et al.*⁵. Commercially available 2,2'-

bipyridine (2) was converted to its *N,N'*-dioxide (3) by refluxing with 30% hydrogen peroxide in glacial acetic acid⁶. The *N,N'* dioxide (3) so obtained, on heating with potassium nitrate/sulphuric acid mixture gave 4,4'-dinitro-2,2'-bipyridine-*N,N'*-dioxide (4). This compound was converted to 4,4'-dichloro-2,2'-bipyridine (1) on refluxing with acetyl chloride followed by deoxygenating of *N,N'*-dioxide with phosphorous trichloride (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Condensation of 4-methyl pyridine (5) with 10% palladium on charcoal gave 4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-bipyridine (6) which on oxidation with potassium permanganate followed by treatment with saturated aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate afforded sodium salt of 4,4'-dicarboxy-2,2'-bipyridine^{4c} (8) (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

The ligands 2-methyl-3-(2-hydroxybenzylamino)-quinolin-(3*H*)-4-one, (MHBQ) (11) and 2-phenyl-3-(2-hydroxybenzylamino)quinolin-(3*H*)-4-one, (PHBQ) (14) are prepared as per the procedures cited in the literature⁷.

The first step in the preparation of MHBQ (11) involves the condensation of anthranilic acid with acetic anhydride. The resulting 2-methylbenzoxazin-4-one (9) on refluxing with hydrazine hydrate yielded 3-amino-2-methylquinazolin-(3*H*)-4-one which on condensation with *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde in acetic acid afforded MHBQ (11) (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

The ligand PHBQ (14) is also prepared by condensing anthranilic acid with benzoyl chloride in pyridine to afford 2-phenylbenzoxazin-4-one (12) which on reaction with hydrazine hydrate followed by condensation with *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde afforded PHBQ (14) as shown in Scheme 5.

Scheme 5

Preparation of metal complexes :

The complexes 15-18 and 26 are prepared according to the literature procedures⁸. In a typical experiment, ruthenium trichloride and excess ligand (nearly four fold

excess) were refluxed in 95% ethanol and the excess solvent is removed under vacuum. The complex was precipitated as the iodide salt by adding saturated aqueous solution of potassium iodide.

L = 4,4'-dichloro-2,2'-bipyridine (1), 2,2'-bipyridine (2), *N,N'*-dioxide of 2,2'-bipyridine (3), 4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-bipyridine (6)

The complex 18 was prepared in a 1 : 1 mixture of methanol-water by refluxing ruthenium trichloride and sodium salt of 4,4'-dicarboxy-2,2'-bipyridine (8).

(15) R = H, (16) R = CH₃
(17) R = Cl, (18) R = CO₂Na

(26)

The procedure of Allen *et al.*⁹ was adopted to synthesize complexes 19-21. Aqueous ruthenium trichloride was treated with hydrazine hydrate at room temperature. The resulting complex [Ru(NH₃)₅Cl]²⁺ when boiled with pyridine or methyl substituted pyridine gave corresponding complexes 19-21.

(19) L = pyridine, (20) L = 4-methylpyridine, (21) L = 3-methylpyridine, RT = room temperature

The complexes **22** and **23** were prepared¹⁰ by refluxing rhodium chloride and the ligand pyridine/4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-bipyridine (**6**) in *N*-ethylmorpholine

(22) L = pyridine, (23) L = 4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-bipyridine

The procedure of Gillard *et al.*¹¹ was utilized in preparing complexes **24** and **25** where the ligands are ethylenediamine and pyridine respectively. The complex **24** is prepared by treating rhodium trichloride in ethanol at 60 °C with ethylenediamine while the complex **25** was obtained by boiling a 1 : 1 mixture of ethanol and 2-methoxy ethanol containing rhodium trichloride and pyridine. After cooling the reaction mixture, ether was added to precipitate the complex **25**.

(24)

(25)

Complexes **27** and **28** were prepared by the method of Lingaiah *et al.*²⁸. The ligands **11** and **14** in acetone are refluxed with $\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4$ ¹³ in toluene. After removing the excess solvent ether is added to precipitate the respective complexes **27** and **28**.

(27) L = MHBQ, (28) L = PHBQ

Preparation of electron relays :

The structures of different electron relays synthesized in this study are given in Scheme 6.

(31) R = H; R' = Allyl, (32) R = Methyl; R' = Allyl
(33) R = H; R' = Benzyl, (34) R = Methyl; R' = Benzyl

Scheme 6

The procedure for the preparation of electron relays was that of Mentha *et al.*⁴. Excess alkyl halide was refluxed with corresponding bipyridine compound in anhydrous methanol and the resulting crude electron relay was recrystallized from water-acetone mixture. The compounds **29** and **31-34** were prepared by this method. The compound **35**¹⁵ was prepared by refluxing 2,2'-bipyridine in 1,2-dibromoethane and compound **36** by refluxing 4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-bipyridine (**6**) with 1,2-dibromoethane in nitrobenzene. The method of preparation of compounds **22** and **23** has already been described in the previous section. The compound **30** is commercially available and was used as such. The typical equation for the preparation of electron relay is shown below :

N,N'-Dialkyl-2,2'-bipyridiniumdihalide

Colloidal platinum on polyvinylalcohol was prepared starting from hexachloroplatinic acid (H_2PtCl_6) using the

procedure of Sasse *et al.*¹⁶. Colloidal ruthenium on poly(vinylalcohol) was prepared from ruthenium trichloride by the procedure of Grätzel *et al.*¹⁷. The three electron donors employed in the present study viz. ethylenediaminetetraacetate (EDTA), triethanolamine (TEOA) and *N*-ethylmorpholine are commercially available. The typical sequence of reactions involved in photochemical cleavage of water molecules are : tris(2,2'-bipyridine) Ru^{II} dication (**15**) after absorbing sunlight gets excited and becomes $\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipyridine})_3^{2+}$. The excited complex can transfer an electron to a suitable acceptor and itself gets converted to $\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipyridine})_3^{3+}$. The reduced form of electron acceptor can generate the hydrogen by the cleavage of water molecules in the presence of suitable co-catalyst. In the process the electron acceptor recycles back to its original state. Conversion of $\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipyridine})_3^{3+}$ to $\text{Ru}(2,2'\text{-bipyridine})_3^{2+}$ is achieved by the sacrificial electron donor present in the system (Scheme 1).

Experimental procedure to determine the rate and volume of photochemical evolution of hydrogen :

As already mentioned, the presence of (1) a photosensitizer, (2) an electron relay, (3) a sacrificial electron donor and (4) a co-catalyst are required for photochemical production of hydrogen from water.

We have carried out several experiments using different permutation and combination of the different components mentioned above. The ruthenium complexes are found to be sensitive in the visible region i.e. 350–700 nm and in this respect sunlight is found to be ideal which covers the entire range of visible spectrum. The four components i.e. photosensitizer ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$), electron relay ($4 \times 10^{-2} M$), sacrificial electron donor ($2 \times 10^{-2} M$) and co-catalysts ($5 \times 10^{-5} M$) are mixed together in a single necked pyrex round bottomed flask fitted with a cone. A tigon tubing is inserted into the cone which leads into the burette filled with water and kept in a trough of water. The contents of the flask are stirred with a magnetic stirrer. The system is then exposed to sunlight and the evolution of hydrogen is recorded from time to time from the displacement of water in the burette. A correction was made for air expansion due to heat radiation by setting up a blank experiment. This general experimental procedure is adopted in all the cases.

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